

Leng Kwang and Silewah as extremely cool tolerant. The two varieties were crossed with a japonica breeding line, Hokkai 241, to incorporate their

tolerance into japonica rices. The F₁ plants of the cross Leng Kwang/Hokkai 241 had high spikelet sterility, and those of Silewah/Hokkai 241 had high spikelet

fertility. Leng Kwang is a promising parent for indica rice breeding programs to improve cool tolerance; Silewah is promising for japonica breeding programs.

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Effect of nontoxic chemicals on brown spot disease in rice seedlings

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The performance of 15 chemicals, known as phytoalexin inducers for different plant species, in inducing resistance to the brown spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae* in susceptible rice plants was evaluated.

Three-week-old seedlings of the rice variety Dharial were sprayed with solutions of the test chemicals at concentrations that have little or no effect on spore germination at 2 days before inoculation. Promising chemicals

were used in subsequent 24-hour seed soaking before sowing and in 24-hour root-dip treatment of 3-week-old seedlings before transplanting. The transplanted seedlings were left exposed to natural infection and the disease reaction was assessed 2 to 5 weeks later. The seedlings raised from treated seeds were grown in pots and spray inoculated, and the disease reaction was assessed 3 or 5 weeks later. Most of the test chemicals gave considerable protection to rice seedlings in different treatments (see table).

With foliage spray, symptoms were reduced by 42-92%. The most effective chemicals were sodium malonate, DL-methionine, and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA).

The seedlings derived from seed treatments developed 35 to 60% fewer symptoms after 3 weeks. In the field, such seedlings also showed considerable resistance; they had 33 to 88% fewer symptoms after 3 weeks. The protective effect declined with time, particularly for barium chloride and nickel nitrate.

Transplanted seedlings in different treatments developed 19 to 50% fewer symptoms after 2 weeks and 12 to 32% fewer symptoms after 5 weeks.

The effectiveness of the phytoalexin inducers in developing resistance in rice seedlings is evident. Although foliage spray is effective, the significant persistence of the induced protective effect in the seedlings until 3 to 5 weeks after the seed treatment and, to a lesser

Mean disease index^a of *Helminthosporium oryzae* infection^b in rice seedlings (variety Dharial) treated with chemicals known as phytoalexin inducers.

Chemical	Concn.	Mean disease index (%)					
		Foliage spray (pot experiment)	Seed soaking			Seedling root-dip (field expt)	
			Pot expt (3 weeks)	Field expt		2 weeks	5 weeks
			3 weeks	5 weeks			
Water (control)		100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Barium chloride	10 ⁻³ M	42.3	51.9	66.0	90.6	62.1	13.5
Ferric chloride	10 ⁻⁴ M	43.2	40.0	11.3	56.5	65.1	78.4
Cadmium chloride	10 ⁻⁴ M	49.8	53.4	63.2	62.1	53.4	14.7
Mercuric chloride	10 ⁻⁵ M	58.2	64.5	41.2	55.2	81.1	88.0
Chromium chloride	10 ⁻³ M	55.0	—	—	—	—	—
Nickel nitrate	10 ⁻⁵ M	31.7	43.0	67.0	90.4	73.8	83.2
Sodium malonate	10 ⁻⁴ M	8.0	54.1	58.5	68.3	50.0	61.4
Sodium molybdate	10 ⁻⁴ M	41.6	43.7	44.3	92.4	56.8	71.3
Sodium iodoacetate	10 ⁻⁴ M	49.4	—	—	—	62.1	80.8
Sodium fluoride	10 ⁻³ M	65.9	—	—	—	—	—
DL-methionine	10 ⁻² M	20.3	46.1	52.8	74.5	61.7	80.8
DL-norleucine	10 ⁻² M	34.0	—	—	—	—	—
DL-norvaline	10 ⁻² M	49.4	—	—	—	—	—
Indole-3-acetic acid	10 ⁻⁴ M	21.1	55.1	55.1	55.2	65.6	16.0
2,4,5-trichlorophenoxy-acetic acid	10 ⁻⁴ M	32.5	62.5	—	—	—	—

^a Disease index was calculated for each plant taking into consideration both the number and size of brown spot lesions.

^b In most experiments, plants were artificially inoculated with a heavy inoculum; only in root-dip treatment were they left exposed to natural infection.

extent, after the root-dip treatment, appears to have more practical significance. In most treatments the number of infections was reduced, but in some, lesion expansion was also inhibited

Sporulation in *Drechslera oryzae*

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Brown leaf spot of rice caused by *Drechslera oryzae* is an important disease of rice in Karnataka, India. The pathogen causes small spots or lesions on the leaves. The isolated spots are oblong or oval, dark brown, and scattered along the leaf. *D. oryzae* does not sporulate on infected green leaves or senescent leaves. But when such leaves were detached and the water-soluble components leached out, then sporulation was abundant. Infected leaves are not the inoculum source for glume infection in Karnataka, as the pathogen does not sporulate on the leaves. Hence, a water-soluble component of the leaf spot was presumed to inhibit sporulation. Therefore, the effect of leaching this component with water was tested.

The cut ends of rice leaves were immersed in distilled water in a flask for 48 hours at room temperature and at 30, 35, 40, and 45°C. Water in the flask was changed at six hourly intervals. The leaves were then removed and kept in a moist chamber. Abundant sporulation from the leaf spots was evident within 48 hours, but the pathogen was killed at 45°C. That indicates that the leaf spots may contain a water-soluble component that inhibits sporulation. ■

Effect of carbon sources on sporulation of *Drechslera oryzae*

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The effect of arabinose, carboxy-cellulose, fructose, galactose, glucose, mannose, rhamnose, ribose, starch, sucrose, and

xylose on sporulation was tested from 0.5 to 9.0% levels by replacing sucrose in Richard's medium. Sporulation was observed in the media containing mannose, starch, and sucrose. The fungus showed limited sporulation in the media with sucrose at 2.5% level. Sporulation was completely suppressed at 3.5%. Maximum sporulation was obtained with mannose at 2.5% concentration and with starch at 6.5%. ■

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Antagonistic action of soil microbes on *Drechslera oryzae*

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Trichoderma sp. isolated from semidry and puddled soils parasitized *Drechslera oryzae* (Breda de Haan) Subram and Jain, whereas *Streptomyces* sp. isolated from the two soils showed inhibitory action on *D. oryzae*, *Bacillus* sp.—present in puddled soil, but not in semidry soil — showed inhibitory action when inoculated on *D. oryzae* on petri plates.

Survival of *Drechslera oryzae* in an aerobic condition

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An experiment on the growth and survival of *Drechslera oryzae* was conducted with the following treatments.

1. Slants with agar medium plugged with cotton dipped in pyrogallol acid + 1 N NaOH (to create complete anaerobic conditions).
2. Mouth of the test tube covered with paraffin (to create partial anaerobic conditions).
3. Control (without above treatments).

The pathogen did not grow in the first treatment and was killed in less than 7 days. When the mouth of the test tube was covered with paraffin, there was growth and the pathogen survived for 4 weeks. But in the control treatment, growth was excellent and *D. oryzae* survived for 18 weeks. This experiment was conducted to verify whether *D. oryzae* can survive in completely or partially anaerobic conditions, as those that prevail in puddled soils. According to these results it can be assumed that *D. oryzae* may not survive for a long time in paddy soil and the fungus in the soil may not serve as a source of inoculum. ■

A soft rot disease of rice observed at IRRI

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In 1978, a soft rot disease was observed on plants of IR129-192-2 in the International Rice Yield Nursery grown at IRRI. Infection was evident from the early to the maximum tillering stages. The infected plants' leaf sheaths and tissues from the basal internodes showed browning and water soaking, accompanied by rotting and a foul odor. The symptoms suggested that bacteria caused the infection, which was similar to an infection observed on IR36 in 1977.

Infected tissues were isolated on potato sucrose agar and incubated at 30°C for 48 hours. Two distinct colony types, Type A and Type B, were apparent on the agar plates. Type A colony was milky white and flat with irregular margins. Type B colony was creamy yellow and slightly raised with irregular margins. On peptone sucrose agar plates, Type B was creamy white to very light yellow. Its surface was slightly raised and rough; the margin was irregular. In addition, a brown pigment diffused to the medium 3 days after incubation. Both colony types produced gas on Wakimoto's medium, produced fluorescent pigment on the same medium under ultraviolet light, and caused potato slices to rot.

A pathogenicity test with 24-hour